

**CHEMICAL INTERACTION BETWEEN SILICON CARBIDE NICALON FIBRES
AND LIQUID ALUMINUM OR ALUMINUM-SILICON ALLOYS**

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ABSTRACT

The present paper reports on the results of a detailed investigation on the chemical reactions that occur at 1000 K between coreless SiC fibres (Nicalon) and pure or 14.5 at% Si-alloyed aluminum melts. Heated at 1000 K, mixtures of milled fibres with Al powder give rise to the formation of free silicon, α -alumina, α and β -silicon carbide and aluminum carbide. Alloying the Al powder with 14.5 at% Si results in the production of the same compounds. From the relative variations in the composition of metal/fibre mixtures, heat-treated for 1 to 1250 h, an interaction mechanism is proposed. One of the main features of this mechanism is the transient formation of aluminum carbide even when thermodynamically impossible. This phenomenon due to the presence of free carbon in the fibres results in large differences in the extent, morphology and composition of the interfacial reaction zone, according to whether the Nicalon fibres react with pure Al or with an Al-Si alloy.

INTRODUCTION

As a general rule, the mechanical properties and the corrosion resistance of metal matrix composite materials are closely related to the chemical reactions that occur at the fibre-matrix interface during their elaboration and uses [1]. A thorough understanding of interface chemistry is thus important in the development of these materials.

In the case of Al matrix composites reinforced with pure SiC, the interface chemistry is rather simple : at temperatures lower than 923 ± 3 K, SiC is in equilibrium with solid Al, while it is readily

attacked by Al at temperatures higher than 923 K, according to the reaction :

At completion, this reaction results in a three-phased monovariant equilibrium, which involves unreacted SiC, Al_4C_3 and a ternary Al-C-Si liquid phase with a very low carbon content [2]. The amount of Si in this liquid phase increases regularly with the temperature from 1.5 at% Si at 923 K to 4.8 ± 0.5 at% Si at 1000 K [2]. Hence, a proper addition of Si to the Al matrix can prevent the foregoing reaction during the elaboration of these composites by liquid-metal infiltration.

The interface chemistry in Al matrix composites, strengthened with Nicalon multifilament fibres [3], is somewhat more complicated as these fibres contain, in addition to SiC, appreciable amounts of Si, C and O, both in the form of free carbon and SiO_2 [3-5] and in the form of a ternary oxycarbide SiC_xO_y [6]. Therefore, other reactions between these constituents and Al are likely to proceed simultaneously with reaction (1), contributing to the decrease in tensile strength of the fibres [7, 8].

The present paper reports the results of an experimental investigation focussed on the chemical reactions that occur at 1000 K between Nicalon fibres and a liquid phase consisting either of pure Al or of an Al-14.5 at% Si alloy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Metal fibre mixtures were prepared from commercial Al powder (99wt%, $d < 45 \mu\text{m}$), Si powder (99.5 wt%, $d < 45 \mu\text{m}$) and coreless SiC Nicalon fibres supplied by Nippon Carbon Co. As determined by photoemission spectroscopy, the chemical composition of these fibres in mol% was the following : SiC = 24 ; free C = 42 ; $\text{SiO}_2 = 12$; $\text{SiO}_x\text{C}_y = 22$ [6]. The mixtures were : cold-pressed at 500 MPa for 10 min, placed in Al_2O_3 boats, heated at 1000 K for 1 to 1250 h in a SiO_2 -closed tube filled with argon, and finally rapidly cooled.

The reacted samples were cut, diamond polished and examined by optical metallography, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and classical X-ray diffraction techniques (XRD). From XRD patterns recorded in normalised conditions, a semi-quantitative analysis of the reaction

products was performed by measuring the intensity of at least three selected reflections of each phase identified in the sample and by referring to the intensities of the corresponding reflections of the pure phase.

Electron microprobe analyses (EMA) were carried out using a Cameca Camebax microprobe equipped with a wavelength dispersive spectrometer and a Tracor Northern 2000 analyser. An operating voltage of 5 kV, a regulated beam current about 40 nA and a counting interval of 10 s were selected. In all cases, the counting rates were corrected for background. The typical counting rates recorded in these conditions for the pure elements and compounds concerned in this work are reported in Table I.

After having corrected the results according to a previous calibration performed in identical conditions with Al-Si standards, the averaged Si content in the metal matrix surrounding the fibres was calculated from the counting rates recorded in different areas for Al and Si in a broad-field scan mode. Concentration profiles for Al, C, O and Si in the metal-fibre reaction zones were established using a fixed-focus electron beam, to measure point by point the counting rates from the four elements along transverse sections of the fibres. The 2- μ m step chosen for it was in the order of the lateral resolution anticipated at the operating voltage of 5 kV.

TABLE 1
Counting rates, in count per second, obtained by EMA for Al, C, O and Si in pure elements and compounds.

Element or compound	Al (c/s)	C (c/s)	O (c/s)	Si (c/s)
Al	1008			
C		2009		
Si				888
SiC		488		616
Al ₂ C ₃	670	372		
Al ₂ O ₃	510			777

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Metal-fibre Interaction Mechanism

In the first series of experiments, mixtures containing 28 wt% of milled Nicalon fibres and 72 wt% of either pure or 14.5 at% Si-alloyed Al powder were heated at 1000 K for different lengths of time, from 1 to 1250 h. Examination of the reacted samples by XRD and EMA led to the following results.

Silicon, aluminum carbide Al_4C_3 , β -cubic and α -hexagonal silicon carbide SiC and α -rhombohedral alumina Al_2O_3 were characterised as reaction products in the Al/Nicalon specimens. The relative variations of the X-ray intensities reported in Fig. 1a show that when the reaction time increases, greater amounts of crystalline SiC and Al_2O_3 are produced, whereas Si and Al_4C_3 go through a maximum at a reaction time of about 200 h and then decrease. As determined by EMA, the Si content in the metal matrix was 7.7 and 5.5 at% at reaction times of 200 and 1250 h, respectively. Referring to a previous study of the thermodynamics in the Al-C-O-Si quaternary system [9], a four-phase equilibrium involving Al_4C_3 , Al_2O_3 , SiC and an Al-Si liquid phase with a Si content of 4.8 at% must be attained for Al/Nicalon specimens heated at 1000 K. It appears from Fig. 1a that the expected phases are truly formed; but their proportions, as well as the Si content in the Al matrix, are still changing at a reaction time of 1250 h. This means that a low reaction rate impedes equilibrium to be reached.

The same reaction products as the previous were found by XRD in Al-Si/Nicalon samples heat-treated at 1000 K. Nevertheless, the X-ray intensities reported in Fig. 1b are fairly different from those of Fig. 1a: Al_2O_3 and crystalline SiC grow faster, Al_4C_3 go again through a maximum but at a shorter reaction time in the order of 50 h whereas Si continuously decreases from the initial value of 14.5 at% to about 6.5 at% at a reaction time of 1250 h. At this reaction time, the composition of the Al-Si/Nicalon system is in agreement with that thermodynamically expected, i.e. a three-phased equilibrium involving Al_2O_3 , SiC and a liquid phase with a Si content of 6.3 at%.

From these results, which support and complete previous investigations [7, 8], two reaction schemes can be proposed according to

whether the Nicalon fibres react with pure Al or with an Al-Si alloy.

When Nicalon fibres react with pure Al, all the chemical substances present in the fibres are simultaneously attacked in accordance with the following set of reactions :

Figure 1. X-ray intensities of the phases produced in (a) Al/Nicalon and (b) Al-14.5 at% Si/Nicalon specimens reacted at 1000 K.

In our experimental conditions, this scheme corresponds to the first 200 h of reaction for Al/Nicalon samples in which only Al_2O_3 and Al_4C_3 are produced, with Si dissolving in the Al matrix. This remains valid as long as the Si content in the Al matrix is lower than 4.8at% at a reaction temperature of 1000 K. Indeed, if this content goes over that value, reaction (1) becomes thermodynamically forbidden, and another reaction scheme takes place, involving reactions (2) (3) (4) and the following additional reaction :

The latter reaction scheme governs the interaction process in the Al-Si/Nicalon specimens heated at 1000 K regardless of the reaction time and begins to act in Al/Nicalon specimens at a reaction time of 200 h. Reaction (5), which is the reverse of reaction (1), is responsible for the formation of crystalline α and β -SiC via a dissolution-recrystallisation process. Furthermore, the transient formation of Al_4C_3 in excess, observed in both Al and Al-Si/Nicalon specimens, can be understood assuming that reaction (5) proceeds at a much lower rate than reaction (2) : this is supported by the results of a recent study of the interaction between carbon fibres and Al-Si alloys [10].

The Metal-fibre Reaction Zone

Further experiments were carried out in order to get more detailed

Figure 2. Optical micrographs of Nicalon fibres heated at 1000 K for 95 h in an Al matrix.

information on the morphology and composition of the fibre-matrix reaction zone. In these experiments, a few Nicalon filaments were cold pressed with a large excess of either pure or 14.5 at% Si-alloyed Al powders and heat-treated at 1000 K for 95 h. After rapid cooling, the resulting samples were cut in a direction perpendicular to the filament axis and examined by optical metallography, SEM and EMA.

Results obtained with Nicalon filaments heated in a pure Al matrix are reported in Fig. 2 and 3. A continuous reaction zone about 2- μm thick can be seen at the fibre-matrix interface in Fig. 2. The concentration profiles reported in Fig. 3 confirm that this reaction

Figure 3. EMA concentration profiles along a transverse section of a Nicalon filament heated at 1000 K for 95 h in an Al matrix.

zone consists of a mixture of Al_2O_3 and Al_4C_3 microcrystals, produced in a direct interaction between liquid Al and the different constituents of the fibres, according to the first reaction scheme proposed previously. The silicon liberated in reactions (1), (3) and (4) is supposed to migrate by solid state diffusion through the reaction zone before dissolving in the Al liquid phase in excess. Indeed, there is no evidence for the infiltration of this liquid phase into the reaction zone, which appears to act as a diffusion barrier that slows down the interaction process.

Fig. 4 and 5 present the results obtained when Nicalon filaments are heat-treated in the presence of an Al-14.5 at% Si alloy. It is clearly visible in Fig.4 that the filaments are far less uniformly and more readily attacked than previously, resulting in a broader reaction zone in the order of 4 to 7 μm in thickness. As a consequence, the thinnest filaments are entirely attacked. Moreover, faceted crystals are observed to grow near the reaction zone but in the bulk of the Al-Si matrix : these were identified as Al_2O_3 and SiC crystals by EMA. The concentration profiles reported in Fig.5 indicate that the reaction zone consists of a heterogeneous mixture of Al_2O_3 , Al_4C_3 and probably SiC crystals, embedded in a silicon-rich Al-Si alloy. The particular morphology of this reaction zone can be understood by considering the sequence of reactions implied in the second foregoing reaction scheme. In an early stage, a first layer containing Al_2O_3 , Al_4C_3 and unreacted

Figure 4. Optical micrographs of Nicalon filaments heated at 1000 K for 95 h in an Al-14.5 at% Si matrix.

SiC is rapidly formed at the metal-fibre interface, according to reactions (2), (3) and (4). If stable, this layer could protect the fibre from further interaction, as in the former case. However, the Al_4C_3 contained in this layer is not in equilibrium with the Al-Si liquid phase. Then, it is slowly converted into SiC and Al according to reaction (5). As a dissolution-recrystallization process is involved in the latter reaction, pores are opened in the first layer, which enables the permeation of the liquid phase into the reaction zone. Hence, this reaction zone develops further, while C and O migrate by liquid-phase diffusion from that zone to Al_2O_3 and SiC crystals growing outwards.

Figure 5. EMA concentration profiles along a transverse section of a Nicalon filament heated at 1000 K for 95 h in an Al- 14.5 at% Si alloy.

CONCLUSION

From the above results, it can be concluded that the use of an Al-Si alloy instead of pure Al for the liquid metal infiltration of Nicalon fibres cannot prevent the fibre-matrix interaction, as would be the case if these fibres were made of pure SiC. On the contrary, a broader reaction zone is formed when Nicalon fibres react with an Al-Si alloy instead of pure Al. This is mainly due to the presence of free carbon in these fibres, which gives rise to the transient formation of Al_4C_3 , even when thermodynamically impossible.

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